

**AN EARLY WARNING SYSTEM TO MONITOR STRATA BEHAVIOUR
AND PREDICT ROOF FALL IN UG COAL MINES DURING COAL
EXTRACTION**

P. Rajpurohit^a, M. R. Saharan^{a*}, D. Lohar^b and K.G. Sharma^c

^a- CSIR-Central Institute of Mining & Fuel Research Institute, Barwa Road, Dhanbad-826001

^b- Department of Mines and Geology, Udaipur, Rajasthan

^c - Indian Institute of Technology, Delhi

*- Corresponding Author Email: maniramsaharan@gmail.com

Purpose: Since ages, underground mining for tabular deposits is a two-step process, namely – development and final extraction / winning. It is imperative in the process that the roof rock strata during development keeps its integrity intact whereas the roof rock strata must lose its integrity in a short span of period after the final extraction / winning process. There always exist ample scope and time for quantification of ground control measures during the process of the development of the tabular deposits through plurality of instruments meant to measure deformation / strain / stress. The

INDIA INTERNATIONAL SCIENCE FESTIVAL 2016

Abstract: December 07-11, 2016, CSIR-NPL

process of the final extraction / winning, however, is rapid one and in combination of the workplace environment there hardly any scope exists for quantification of the corrective ground control measures. The best adopted policy for safety during the final extraction / winning process is to evacuate the work place till the void created beyond the active working zone (known as goaf in the mining parlance) fell and resume the working thereafter. Accordingly, it is imperative for the safety of the final extraction / winning process of the tabular ore bodies that an adequate load monitoring and pre-warning telltale system shall be developed.

Methods: A mining prop, PADM (Prop for Abutment Deformation Measurement), has been developed which observe, record, communicate and provide alarm for impending threat of roof fall. It is combination of mechanical and an electronic system which consists of sensors and transmitter section mounted on a spring actuated mining prop and it needs to be placed at the goaf edge during initial installation. The data receiver with data logger are placed at a safe remote location and routers to increase the transmission range in the designed system. The system displays the deformation value in millimeter along with safe, intermediate and danger zone indicators and provides audio visual alarms in danger zone at goaf edge and at a safe remote location. The deformation value is logged with timestamps at the safe remote location for further studies. The data is transmitted from goaf edge to the safe remote location using unlicensed industrial, scientific and medical 2.4 GHz band for wireless RF signal transmission.

Results: Development of PADM solve age old issue of monitoring abutment deformation and stresses. It is now possible to reliably observe, record, communicate and obtain pre-set alarms those assist in modifying the coal extraction method and ratio while maintaining the essential safety.

Conclusion: A mining prop, acronym PADM, with capability of on-site real time abutment deformation measurement system has been developed. The PADM is to solve age-old issue of reliable abutment deformation measurement system which is hitherto unknown. The PADM will assist in improving safety and productivity of coal extraction from bord and pillar mining in underground which is the main extraction method.

Keywords: bord and pillar mining, goaf edge, abutment deformation, underground coal mining.
